

Protocol OCPRIIP

Answer to Review

Matteo Guenci^{*1}, Daniele Spedicati^{†2}, Chiara Parravicini^{‡3}, and
Nicole Liggeri^{§4}

^{1,2,3,4}University of Bologna, Italy

May 9, 2024

1 Response to Review

In response to Salvatore Di Marzo. (2024). Review of: "Protocol OCPRIIP". Qeios. doi:10.32388/KMLZ4H.

We appreciate the thoughtful review and the constructive suggestions provided. Your feedback has been carefully considered, and we have made revisions to our protocol accordingly.

1.1 Protocol Adjustments

Correction in Step 3.3: We have addressed the slip identified in this step by revising the text. Specifically, we replaced "The DOIs of the reviews and the reviewed entities become DOI URLs, while the IRI of the Citations" with "The DOIs of the reviews and the reviewed entities are converted to DOI URLs, while the IRI of the Citations serve as the Entity subjects of our triples." We have improved the clarity of our Data Analysis section by providing specific goals for each analysis.

1.2 Ongoing Tasks

Peer Review Venue Analysis: Our next task involves examining the number of venues receiving peer reviews to understand their prevalence and utilization. By comparing this data with OpenCitations Meta, we aim to gain insights into the communication between these two Open Science tools.

^{*}Corresponding author: matteo.guenci@studio.unibo.it

[†]Corresponding author: daniele.spedicati@studio.unibo.it

[‡]Corresponding author: chiara.parravicini@studio.unibo.it

[§]Corresponding author: nicole.liggeri@studio.unibo.it

1.3 Approach to Data Gathering

Given recent developments in our project, we have opted for reproducibility by relying on the 2023 Crossref dump instead of continuously updated data. This decision ensures consistency, as using our software with the Crossref API would yield varied results due to ongoing data updates. Consequently, the “crossref_commons.py” library will no longer be part of our workflow.

In consideration of convenience and hardware limitations during development, we have decompressed the sizable Crossref dump (approximately 186 gigabytes compressed) into 18 smaller, more manageable packages.

1.4 Workflow Management in COCI

It’s important to note that the COCI workflow will be adapted to suit our case study, as it was originally designed for different purposes and is currently outdated.

1.5 Future Research Findings

Rather than providing speculative examples, we prefer to await the specific results generated by our software. Our primary objective at this stage is to deliver a tool for comparing two platforms’ coverage of citation information.

1.6 Revised version

The revised version of the manuscript is ”<http://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.261ge56qwg47/v2>”